

ON CROSS-PLY CRACKING IN GRAPHITE,
GLASS AND ARAMID FIBRE-REINFORCED
EPOXY LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

The transverse tensile strength of a unidirectional laminate is generally accepted as a material parameter. Cracking in transverse plies of a laminate, however, cannot simply be predicted with this material property, as it is influenced by many parameters, like e.g. the thermal strain, the void distribution and the constraining effect of neighbouring layers. This investigation describes qualitatively the effect of these parameters on cross-ply cracking in graphite, glass and aramid fibre-reinforced epoxy.

INTRODUCTION

Cross-ply cracking in transverse plies of angle-ply laminates of fibre-reinforced plastics is influenced by many parameters. Most important are:

1. the properties of the fibre
2. the properties of the matrix
3. the fibre volume
4. the quality of the interface
5. the defect distribution
6. the constraining influence of neighbouring layers.

Most important fibre properties in relation with cross-ply cracking are the stiffness and thermal expansion coefficient perpendicular to the fibre direction. Table 1 summarizes the properties of the respective fibres of this investigation.

The stiffness perpendicular to the fibre, being larger than the stiffness

of the matrix, gives rise to a strain magnification in the matrix, if the laminate is loaded perpendicular to the fibre direction. Based on an idealized square array of the fibres Kies [1] developed a model to determine the strain magnification factor as a function of fibre and

Table 1:

The elastic constants and thermal expansion coefficients $\alpha_{//}$ and α_{\perp} of the fibres of the different materials [2].

Fibre	$E_{//}$ (GPa)	E_{\perp} (GPa)	$G_{//\perp}$ (GPa)	$\alpha_{//}$ $\times 10^{-6} / ^{\circ}\text{C}$	α_{\perp}
E-Glass	73	73	30	5	5
Aramid	133	5.4	12	-4	59
C-Fibre (HT)	240	15	50	-0.5	10

matrix properties and fibre volume. The strain magnification factor based on this model is given by

$$\text{SMF} = 1 / \left(1 - \left(1 - \frac{E_m}{E_{\perp}} \right) \sqrt{\frac{4V_f}{\pi}} \right) \quad (1)$$

with V_f is the fibre volume and E_m , E_{\perp} are the moduli of the matrix and of the fibre perpendicular to the fibre direction, respectively.

As an example the strain magnification factor for a composite with $E_m = 4.00 \text{ GPa}$ and a fibre volume of $V_f = 0.65$ measures 7.13 3.00 and 1.31 for glass, graphite and aramid fibre-reinforced epoxy respectively.

Glass-epoxy shows, because of the high modulus of the glass fibre in transverse direction, the highest strain magnification factor. Now the 90-deg ply fracture strain could be calculated roughly, if the fracture strain of the matrix is known. Because of e.g. the actual irregular fibre distribution, non-homogeneous thermal strains, an imperfect fibre-matrix bond, voids and the constraining effect of neighbouring layers this calculated strength can be far from reality. Before a realistic approximation of the 90-deg ply strength can be made, the influence of the above mentioned parameters should be investigated. This has hardly been done for available commercial fibre reinforced plastic systems. One of the reasons is, that it is almost impossible to vary one specific parameter without also changing the others.

One aspect which was investigated recently is the constraining effect of neighbouring layers. It was found, that the strength of a 90-deg ply in an angle-ply laminate is higher than the transverse strength of a unidirectional laminate [3, 4]. The increase is small when the 90-deg ply is thick and when the stiffness of the neighbouring layers is small. The increase is strongest for thin 90-deg plies if they are embedded between the stiff 0- deg layers. This constraining effect not only results in an increase in strength of the 90-deg ply, but also in a decrease of the scatter of the strength (increase of shape parameter) [5].

The strength distribution of 90-deg plies was found from single specimens, by considering the specimen to consist of a chain of small specimens (elements) all of which can fail.

This technique is also applied in the present investigation, which deals with cross-ply cracking in aramid-, glass- and graphite-epoxy. Two-parameter Weibull-distributions for the respective 90-deg plies are determined. From these strength distributions the influence of some of the above mentioned parameters, like fibre, voids and constraint on cross-ply cracking are determined qualitatively.

MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTS

The materials, produced from prepregs of different suppliers, are cured under the conditions presented in Table 2.

The laminates are produced by DFVLR-Braunschweig making use of an autoclave. To obtain a flat laminate surface a 5 mm thick aluminium plate was put on top of the bleeder material (or in case of the no-bleed systems on top of the release fabric) inside the vacuum bag. From the produced plates 16 mm wide and 200 mm long specimens were cut with a diamond wheel. The specimens were dried and stored in a dessicator. The tests were performed in a displacement-controlled (2 mm/min) Instron testing machine with mechanical grips. In the gripping area the specimens were reinforced with 40 mm long aluminium alloy taps, leaving a free length of 120 mm. Cracking of the 90-deg ply in the graphite-epoxy laminates was detected with a piezo-electric load cell in connection with a computer, which stores the signal above a certain threshold.

Cracking in the aramid-epoxy and in the thinner glass-epoxy laminates cannot be detected with the piezo-electric load cell. This, because crack formation and growth is stable, which do not lead to a sudden load drop.

For this reason in these cases crack formation was studied at the polished edge of some specimens. These specimens were stepwise loaded and unloaded up to increasing levels of strain and the number of cracks in the gage length (l = 50 mm) are counted.

Table 2:
The autoclave cure cycle for the different material systems

Prepreg	cure cycle		Pressure (kPa)	Postcure	
	Temp (° C)	Time (hr)		Temp (° C)	Time (hr)
graphite-epoxy T300 / 914 C	175	1	700	190	4
IM6 / 6376 no bleed	175	2.5	600	---	---
glass-epoxy	125	2	300	---	---
	125	2	700	---	---
aramid-epoxy	175	2	700	---	---

ANALYSIS

The method to determine the strength distribution of 90-deg plies from a single specimen was described earlier [5,7], so it is repeated only briefly here. The occurrence of multiple cracking in the 90-deg ply before the specimen finally fails, makes it reasonable to consider the 90-deg ply to consist of a chain of elements all of which can fail. Crucial in this technique is the determination of the number of elements in a specimen. This is based on the stress distribution near cracks in the 90-deg ply. This stress distribution is calculated with the aid of a shear lag analysis the element of which is given in Figure 1. The shear stress, which introduces again the stress in the broken 90-deg ply, is active in the shear transfer layer, a resin-rich area at the 0-deg/90-deg ply interface.

The stress in the 90-deg ply (ply 2) at a distance x from the crack was found to be:

$$\sigma_{2,x} = \sigma_{2,\infty} (1 - \exp \gamma x) \quad (2)$$

where

$$\gamma = \sqrt{\frac{G_m}{b} \left(\frac{1}{E_1 a_1} + \frac{2}{E_2 a_2} \right)} \quad (3)$$

Figure 1. Element of the applied shear lag analysis

the elastic constants G_m , E_1 and E_2 are the shear modulus of the matrix, the modulus of the 0-deg ply and the modulus of the 90-deg ply respectively. The dimensions b , a_1 and a_2 are the thickness of the shear transfer layer, the 0-deg and 90-deg ply, respectively.

The maximum shear stress, which occurs in the shear transfer layer at the crack tip $(x, y) = (0, \pm a_2/2)$ is

$$\tau_{\max} = \frac{G_m}{b} \cdot \left(\frac{\sigma_{2, \infty}}{E_2 \gamma} \right) \cdot \left(1 + \frac{E_2 a_2}{2E_1 a_1} \right) \quad (4)$$

according to the applied shear lag analysis.

The undisturbed stress $\sigma_{2, \infty}$ consists of a thermal and a mechanical component. The thermal component is calculated with the aid of

$$\sigma_2^t = \frac{\Delta T (\alpha_2 - \alpha_1) a_1 E_1 E_2}{E_2 a_2/2 + E_1 a_1} \quad (5)$$

where α_2 and α_1 , are the thermal expansion coefficients of the 90-deg ply and 0-deg ply respectively, ΔT is the temperature difference between curing and testing temperature. For the materials with unknown thermal expansion coefficients the term $\Delta T(\alpha_2 - \alpha_1)$ was determined from the curvature of unbalanced 0₂/90₂ laminates making use of the theory of a bimetallic strip [6].

Close to an existing crack there will be no more crack formation as the stress here is too low. This leads to the more or less regular crack spacing, which is often observed in laminates with transverse plies. Thus the element length should be of about the size of the crack spacing. In that case the condition that of N existing elements $n < N$ break only once would be satisfied. Another condition is, that the stress in elements with broken neighbours can assumed to be undisturbed. This, however, results in a too large element which fractures more than once. For this reason the element length is somewhat arbitrarily chosen as double the length in which 90 % of the stress in the 90^0 -ply is introduced again. This length follows from equation (2) after substituting $\sigma_{2,x} = 0.9 \sigma_{2,\infty}$. In most cases the element-length is sufficiently short, as the number of cracks n are smaller than the number of elements N . Only in case of the glass-epoxy laminates the crack density is so high, that the element length had to be reduced to half its size.

The next step in the determination process of the strength distribution from the data of one specimen is to measure the fracture strain of every occurring crack. This is done with the piezo-electric load cell, which measures the load drop caused by sudden crack formation. If the crack formation is a slow propagating process the piezo-electric load cell fails to detect cracking, so that in these cases the number of cracks are counted at certain values of applied strain at a polished specimen edge. Results from these experiments are fracture strain data of every occurring crack or of crack j ($j < N$) listed in increasing order of strength. The probability of failure F for the occurrence of crack j now is calculated with

$$F = \frac{j}{N + 1} \quad (6)$$

where N is the total number of elements in the specimen. Now the assumption is made, that the strength distribution can be described by a two parameter Weibull distribution:

$$F = 1 - \exp - (\epsilon_{f,1_0} / \hat{\epsilon}_{f,1_0})^a \quad (7)$$

in which $\hat{\epsilon}_{f,1_0}$ is the characteristic fracture strain and "a" the shape parameter. From equation (7) it is clear that the two-parameter Weibull distribution can be presented as a straight line if $\ln(-\ln(1-F))$ is plot-

ted as a function of $\ln(\epsilon_{f,1})$. The experimental data are plotted this way and a best two parameter Weibull function is determined making use of linear regression technique.

In order to be able to compare the strength distribution of the 90-deg ply elements of a different length the strength distribution is reduced to the length of $l = 1$ mm. This is done with the equation

$$\hat{\epsilon}_{f,V_2} / \hat{\epsilon}_{f,V_1} = (V_1/V_2)^{1/a} \quad (8)$$

which describes the influence of volume (V_1, V_2) on the characteristic strength $\hat{\epsilon}_f$. This equation can also be used to predict the influence of the ply thickness on the strength distribution assuming, that the shape parameter which describes the distribution of defects in the thickness direction a_t is equal to the shape parameter, which describes the defect distribution in length direction a ($a_t = a$).

RESULTS

a) Graphite-epoxy T300/914C

The results on this material are published before [5,7] and thus only the major findings are reported. Data and test results are presented in Table 3. The thermal strain was calculated with $\alpha_1 = 0.8 \times 10^{-6} / ^\circ\text{C}$ and $\alpha_2 = 28.9 \times 10^{-6} / ^\circ\text{C}$ for the 0-deg and 90-deg ply respectively [5]. Making use of equation (2) and (3) the element length was calculated based on the elastic constants $E_1 = 128$ GPa, $E_2 = 9.5$ GPa, $G_m = 1.48$ GPa and on a thickness of the shear transfer layer of $b = 0.015$ mm.

The tests on four specimens per laminate showed relatively low scatter, so that the results clearly fall apart into three groups (for the three laminates). The mean Weibull strength distributions for the 90-deg plies are indicated in the Figure 2. Thinner 90-deg plies show a larger fracture strain (larger than can be predicted with Weibull theory e.g. with $a_t \sim a=6.3$) and a larger Weibull shape parameter. These are the two aforementioned effects of constraint.

b) Graphite-epoxy IM6/6376

The thermal strain in the system IM6/6376 was determined with the aid of an unbalanced laminate. Further the element length is determined with

Table 3:

The thickness of the different plies, thermal strain in the 90-deg ply ϵ_2^t , the element length l_0 , the Weibull shape parameter a , and the characteristic fracture strain $\hat{\epsilon}_f$ (element length = 1 mm), determined from (n) specimens out of the carbon fibre prepreg systems T300/914C and

	a_1 (mm)	a_2 (mm)	ϵ_2^t (%)	l (mm)	a	$\hat{\epsilon}_f$ (%)
IM6/6376						
T300/914C 0 ₂ /90 ₄ /0 ₂	0.263	0.525	0.448	0.69	10.47	1.666 (4)
0 ₂ /90 ₆ /0 ₂	0.254	0.762	0.433	0.83	7.55	1.525 (4)
0 ₂ /90 ₁₂ /0 ₂	0.250	1.549	0.394	1.12	6.41	1.367 (4)
IM6/6376						
0/90 ₄ /0	0.134	0.535	0.492	0.715	11.41	1.629 (3)
0/90 ₆ /0	0.131	0.787	0.467	0.845	13.45	1.636 (2)
0/90 ₁₂ /0	0.133	1.598	0.407	1.124	7.75	1.507 (4)

Figure 2. The probability of failure as a function of the strain for 90-deg ply elements of unit length of the investigated T300/914C system. The dashed lines represent a prediction of the thickness effect with $a_t = 6.34$ and $a_t = 4.59$ respectively, which forces the Weibull strength distribution to intersect the experimental distribution at the characteristic fracture strain $\hat{\epsilon}_f$ (indicated with a plus sign).

equation (2) and (3) with the elastic constants $E_1 = 159.5$ GPa, $E_2 = 9.24$ GPa and $G_m = 1.38$ GPa (calculated from $E_m = 3.6$ GPa [8]) and the thickness of the shear transfer layer $b = 0.015$ mm. The results for the

different 90-deg plies are indicated in Table 3.

The results of four specimens per laminate are presented in Figure 3a, b, c. These specimens show, unlike the system dealt with before, a wide

Figure 3. The Weibull strength distributions for the 90-deg plies of different ply thickness of the graphite/epoxy IM6/6376 (four specimens per laminate)

variation of fracture strain. It was found, that one or two specimens per laminate showed 90-deg ply cracking at a low strain level compared with the others. This indicates a very inhomogeneous defect distribution, locally however concentrated in the laminate in 0-deg orientation. The four specimens with the thinner 90-deg plies (Figure 3a, b) show similar results as the system T300/914C for all thicknesses (see Figure 2), namely cracking at low strain takes place with wide scatter (low shape parameter), whereas the specimens with a higher 90-deg ply strength show less

scatter (larger shape parameter). Two of the four thick specimens show a saturation of cracking (Figure 3c) as above a certain strain level no more cracking occurs. The saturation level is indicated by a dotted line. The other two specimens broke before the saturation level was reached. Mean results of the strength distribution of the different 90-deg plies reduced to an element length of $l = 1$ mm are indicated in Figure 4. In tendency they show a similar behaviour as the system T300/914C; at a decreasing ply thickness the fracture strain and shape parameter increase. The fracture strain of the 90_4 -ply elements, however, mainly is smaller than those of the 90_6 -ply elements. This probably is caused by the wide scatter in test results, which could not be prevented by taking the results of the best specimens.

Figure 4. The mean Weibull strength distribution of 90-deg ply elements of different thickness (element length $l = 1$ mm) out of graphite-epoxy IM6/6376

c) Glass-epoxy

The data and results for the glass-epoxy laminates are presented in Table 4. It shows that the thermal strain is low, as can be expected from the isotropy of the glass fibre. These thermal strains are calculated making use of equation (5) with $\alpha_1 = 8 \times 10^{-6} / ^\circ\text{C}$ and $\alpha_2 = 20 \times 10^{-6} / ^\circ\text{C}$ respectively.

Cross-ply cracking in the glass-epoxy laminates was very severe, so that in every 90-deg ply more cracks developed than the calculated number of

elements. For this reason the element length (defined as double the length in which 90 % of the stress is recovered) was reduced to half its size. Now from the number of elements in the specimen and the available data (number of cracks at certain load levels) the probability of failure was calculated and presented in Figure 5 as a function of the strain. The results indicate, that there is no significant difference between the

Table 4:

Dimensions, elastic constants and test results of the glass-epoxy material. The first line for every laminate gives the data for the material cured at a pressure of 700 kPa and the second line for the material cured at 300 kPa. The elastic constants E_1 , E_2 are determined on a unidirectional laminates cured under the same conditions. They varied with the thickness of the two plates. With the aid of the thus found modulus-thickness relation the stiffness of the separate plies of the 0/90/0 laminates was determined assuming a uniform compaction of the separate plies.

	a_1 (mm)	E_1 (GPa)	a_2 (mm)	E_2 (GPa)	l_0 (mm)	$\frac{t}{\epsilon^2}$ (%)	a	$\hat{\epsilon}_f$ (%)
0/90/0	0.159	44.29	0.159	14.13	0.224	0.101	7.61	0.794
	0.158	44.65	0.159	14.33	0.225	0.101		
0/90 ₂ /0	0.150	47.62	0.302	15.02	0.298	0.089	8.15	0.639
	0.152	46.88	0.303	15.53	0.302	0.088		
0/90 ₄ /0	0.147	48.72	0.589	16.46	0.397	0.068	7.18	0.529
	0.153	46.52	0.609	15.27	0.381	0.071		

laminates cured at a pressure of 700 and 300 kPa, although there is a big difference in void content. The laminates produced at 700 kPa contained less voids; the exact void content, however, is not available yet. Further the laminates show a saturation of cracking at higher fracture strain, except for the laminate with the single 90-deg ply. This saturation is caused by the shear stress, which reaches the shear yield stress or interlaminar shear strength. Other investigations on glass-epoxy [9] also showed this phenomenon.

In the simple 90-deg ply, where saturation of cracking did not occur, the number of cracks at specimen failure was still larger than the number of elements, in spite of the aforementioned reduction of the element length. For this reason the data points with $n > N$ were not considered. Transform-

mation of the test results to a uniform element length $l = 1 \text{ mm}$ led to the Weibull distributions indicated in Figure 6. They show only one aspect of constraint, i.e. the increase in fracture strain at decreasing

5a

5b

5c

Figure 5. The Weibull strength distribution of the 90-deg ply elements of different thickness out of glass-epoxy.

ply thickness. The other aspect, an increasing Weibull shape parameter at decreasing ply thickness, fails. Making use of the Weibull theory for a description of the influence of the ply thickness it is found, that the

shape parameter which describes the influence of the thickness is much lower ($a_t = 3.2 - 3.6$) than the shape parameter which describes the influence of the length ($a = 7$ to 8).

d) Aramid-epoxy

The data and test results of the laminates from aramid-epoxy are presented in Table 5. Because of the large positive thermal expansion coefficient transverse to the fibre and the negative one in fibre direction the thermal strain in the 90-deg ply is very high. The thermal strains were calculated with equation (5) substituting for $\alpha_1 = 4 \times 10^{-6}/^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $\alpha_2 = 57 \times 10^{-6}/^{\circ}\text{C}$ [10].

Figure 6. The Weibull strength distributions of glass-epoxy 90-deg ply elements of unit length with a different thickness. Intermittant drawn distributions are predictions based on the indicated shape parameters a_t .

These thermal strains are so high, that on cutting the laminates cracking already occurred. An optimization of the cutting procedure did not lead to success. For this reason most of the specimens contained cracks before the tensile test was performed. The element length was calculated with equation (2) and (3) substituting the elastic constants, $E_1 = 86.67$ GPa, $E_2 = 3.00$ GPa, $G_m = 1.48$ GPa and for the thickness of the shear transfer layer $b = 0.015$ mm.

The test data lead to Weibull distributions as given in Figure 7. They

show that at the beginning of the static test (when $\epsilon_2 = \epsilon_2^t$) almost all specimens contained cracks. The number of cracks in the gage length of 50 mm are given in parentheses. If the 90-deg ply is precracked the probability of failure increases only slowly up to the point where the probability of failure is the same as for an uncracked specimen. Like glass-epoxy aramid-epoxy also shows a saturation of cracking in the 90-deg plies even in the single 90-deg ply (Figure 7a). This saturation is not only the result of the exceeded matrix yield stress or interlaminar shear strength but also due to formation of cracks in the 90-deg ply in loading direction. This probably is the result of edge stresses of which the component in the thickness direction is most critical.

Table 5:

Dimensions of the different plies, thermal strain in the 90-deg ply, the element length l_0 and the Weibull parameters a and $\hat{\epsilon}_f$ for the investigated aramid-epoxy laminates.

	a_1 (mm)	a_2 (mm)	ϵ_2^t (%)	l_0 (mm)	a	$\hat{\epsilon}_f$ (%)
0/90/0	0.111	0.110	0.918	0.093	7.30	1.366
0/90 ₃ /0	0.104	0.312	0.887	0.177	7.82	1.329
0/90 ₆ /0	0.101	0.606	0.846	0.210	6.64	1.062

The test results indicate, that at a decreasing ply thickness the fracture strain of the ply increases. The shape parameters of the Weibull distributions, however, do not show a significant difference. A determination of the shape parameter a_t , which describes the effect of the ply thickness on the strength is not performed, because of the small number of data and because of the precracked condition of the material.

DISCUSSION

Although cross-ply cracking is dependent on many parameters two of the three types of materials investigated show properties, which are dominated by one parameter. In glass-epoxy cross-ply cracking is dominated by the transverse stiffness of the glass fibre, which gives rise to a high strain magnification factor in the matrix. Cross-ply cracking in aramid-epoxy is dominated by the high residual strain as a result of the high transverse thermal expansion coefficient of the fibre, which is in the range of the thermal expansion coefficient of epoxies. The strong degree

of anisotropy in thermal expansion coefficients thus causes a problem in regard with the curing stresses. Graphite-epoxy shows more balanced

7a

7b

7c

Figure 7. The Weibull strength distribution for 90-deg ply elements of different thickness out of aramid epoxy. The number in parentheses indicates the number of cracks before starting the tensile test.

properties in relation with cross-ply cracking. Due to the smaller anisotropy of the fibre the residual strain is smaller. The strain magnification factor is higher than for aramid-epoxy, but not so high to reduce the 90-deg ply strength strongly. That's why the highest fracture strains are reached by the graphite- epoxy material.

The influence of other parameters like e.g. voids is not quite clear. The

results of the graphite-epoxy IM6/6376 show a large scatter of results, indicating, that the distribution of defects is non-uniform. The big scatter does not occur in the data of one particular specimen, but if the data of all specimens are considered. A small number of specimens show premature cracking causing the complete Weibull distribution curve to be shifted to lower fracture strains. This leads to the conclusion, that the void distribution is preferentially 0-deg oriented. Besides, the observation was made, that the thickest specimens showed premature cracking. These specimens further showed more voids (visible at the polished specimens edge) in the 90-deg plies than thinner specimens. The production technique, using an aluminium plate on top of the release fabric, is the reason for this preferential location of the voids. Probably, thick rovings in the 0-deg ply cause, as a result of the pressure on the plate, a very high pressure on the thick rovings but a small pressure just next to these rovings. In this way in the uncured laminate strong local pressure differences occur, which forces the voids to concentrate in low pressure areas i.e. next to thick rovings. It is interesting to see that the system T300/914C does not show this phenomenon of strong scatter in fracture data among the different specimens [5]. In laminates of the latter systems at the polished specimens edges no voids were found. Thus in contraction to T300/914C the system IM6/6376 shows void formation under the cure conditions as used.

The occurrence of voids gives the possibility to study the influence of these voids. The Weibull distributions, however, show that it has no meaning to determine the strength as a function of a mean value of void content, except when the void distribution is homogeneously distributed in location and size. Further it is of interest, that the influence of voids in glass-epoxy is much less than in graphite-epoxy. A reduction of the void content by increasing the autoclave pressure from 300 to 700 kPa did not lead to a measurable improvement in fracture strain. These investigations on the influence of voids are not yet finished.

Another aspect of cross-ply cracking is the constraining effect of neighbouring layers on 90-deg ply cracking. The system T300/914C showed, that this constraining effect leads to an increase of the strength of thinner 90-deg plies (stronger than can be predicted as a volume effect using Weibull theory) and to an increase of the shape parameter. The same behaviour is found in tendency for the system IM6/6376. Here the constraining effect is less clear, because of the superimposed effect of the inhomoge-

neous distribution of defects. The glass-epoxy and aramid-epoxy also show an increase in strength when the 90-deg ply gets thinner, although an increase in shape parameter could not be found. For glass-epoxy the increase in strength is however stronger than can be predicted, assuming that the defect distribution in thickness direction is similar to the one in length direction (because $a_t < a$ effectively, see Figure 6). This seems to be an aspect of the influence of constraint; the other aspect, the increasing shape parameter, is not found. Thus the question arises, whether the increase of strength at decreasing ply thickness really is an effect of constraint. The only explanation of the rather strong effect of thickness could be the difference in fibre volume. This difference is caused by the fact, that prepreg plies of the same orientation are compacted more than prepreg plies which have a different orientation. This is of course only valid for the material systems with an overamount of resin (bleeding prepregs). The variation of compaction is visible from the variation of a_1 in Table 3 to 6 for the different prepreg systems. The transverse fracture strain of especially glass-epoxy will be influenced by the fibre volume because of the large value of the strain magnification factor. That's why the increase in strength at decreasing ply thickness can in any way partly be explained with the decreasing fibre volume.

The influence of the matrix ductility and interface on cross-ply cracking in graphite-epoxy systems is demonstrated elsewhere [11].

CONCLUSIONS

Cross-ply cracking is a complicated phenomenon in fibre-reinforced plastics. The three investigated material systems show cross-ply cracking dominated by different parameters. Cross-ply cracking in glass-epoxy is mainly caused by the strain magnification factor in the matrix, which is the result of the high transverse stiffness of the fibre. In aramid-epoxy the dominating parameter is the thermal strain, which is close to the fracture strain of the transverse ply. Aramid-epoxy and glass-epoxy (except for the single 90-deg ply) show a saturation of 90-deg ply cracking before specimen failure, whereas graphite-epoxy only shows crack saturation in some cases for the thickest 90-deg ply 90_{12} . It was found, that voids had a strong effect on 90-deg ply cracking in graphite-epoxy but only a small effect in glass-epoxy. The influence of constraint was clear in one particular graphite-epoxy, in the other one it was

superimposed by the inhomogeneous distribution of voids. The influence of constraint in the glass-epoxy and aramid-epoxy is not completely clear.

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